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Biomedical Instrumentation in Vedic Period

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Abstract

In this article, an attempt has been made to correlate between ancient period instruments used for surgery and mechanics used for treatment of the biological systems with the modern period biomedical instrumentation. This paper will provide an insight into Vedic period biomedical instruments and their future scopes. Here, it is also discussed about the surgical instruments during Sushruta period 600 B.C. This paper also discusses about advanced surgical technology during Sushruta period. These were some early practices in India before the invention of the instrumentation techniques and now these early techniques have modernized via biomedical engineering.

Keywords: Dhanvantari, Charaka-Samhita, Shushruta-Samhita, rhinoplasty, Surgical instruments, Ayurveda

Introduction

Ancient Indian System of Medical Sciences, just like other branches of sciences is very rich and has a well-defined conceptual framework that is benefitting mankind consistently throughout the ages. Indians in Vedic times have always advocated the holistic approach towards life which includes all the domains of life including Medical Sciences. Thus unlike present-day allopathy, the Medical Science in Ancient India talks about not just treating the visible and surfaced symptoms of a disease, but the treatment is given with a holistic approach and the root cause of the symptoms is addressed. Indian medicine has a long history which is mentioned in Veda especially in Atharvaveda. Of all the four Vedas- Atharva Veda is said to talk a lot about medical sciences and has around 114 hymns related to this [1]. Ayurveda is mentioned in Atharva Veda. At the early phase of the Vedic period Dhanvantari was defined as a god of medicine [2]. The golden age of Indian medicine, from 800 BCE until about 1000 CE, was marked especially by the production of the medical treatises known as the Charaka-Samhita and Sushruta-Samhita, attributed respectively to Charaka, a physician, and Sushruta, a surgeon. According to Sushruta, the surgeon should be equipped with 20 sharp and 101 blunt instruments of various descriptions. The instruments were largely of steel. Alcohol seems to have been used as a narcotic during operations, and bleeding was stopped by hot oils and tar.

Veda Views about Medicines

The Hindus believed that the body contains three elementary substances, microcosmic representatives of the three divine universal forces, which they called spirit (air), phlegm, and bile (comparable to the humors of the Greeks). Health depends on the normal balance of these three elementary substances. The seven primary constituents of the body—blood, flesh, fat, bone, marrow, chyle, and semen—are produced by the action of the elementary substances [3].

Ayurveda

Atharva Veda is more related to Ayurveda. For example, in Atharva Veda, it is mentioned that a medical practitioner should show his affiliation towards Atharva Veda. Alone Atharva Veda only describes the various ways of treatment like- Daana, Swastan, Mangala, Hom, Niyam, Praayshchitta, Upavasa, Mantra, and so on. All this is connected with Atharva Veda. In Ayurveda, various medical rituals and traditions are mentioned for the cure of diseases [3].

Dhanvantari : god of medicine.

Lord Dhanvantari is an outstanding personality in the history of Ayurveda. He was the physician of the Gods (in both the Vedas and Puranas) and an excellent surgeon. In Hinduism, worshipers pray to Dhanvantari seeking his blessings for sound healing.

Acharya Charak- Father of Medicine 300 BC

Acharya Charak has been crowned as the Father of Medicine. His renowned work, the “Charak Samhita“, is considered as an encyclopedia of Ayurveda. His principles, diagnoses, and cures retain their potency and truth even after a couple of millennia. When the science of anatomy was confused with different theories in Europe, Acharya Charak revealed through his innate genius and enquiries the facts on human anatomy, embryology, pharmacology, blood circulation, and diseases like diabetes, tuberculosis, heart disease, etc.

The following statements are attributed to Acharya Charak:

“A physician who fails to enter the body of a patient with the lamp of knowledge and understanding can never treat diseases. He should first study all the factors, including environment, which influence a patient’s disease, and then prescribe treatment. It is more important to prevent the occurrence of disease than to seek a cure [4].”

Shushruta“Father of Surgery.”

Sushruta, an ancient Indian physician, to the medical field are highly admired. The Sushruta Samhita is also one of the most important surviving ancient treatises on medicine and is also considered a foundational text of the Ayurveda.

Sushruta, the great sage surgeon, philosopher, and teacher of ancient India, practiced around 600 BC. He is renowned all over the world for his contribution to surgery in general and plastic surgery in particular especially rhinoplasty. His contribution to surgical instruments including endoscopes is great. A Literature survey was the basis of this study. Shushruta belonged to a period between 600 and 800 BC. His conception of surgical instruments, the description of their quality, methods of manufacture, and their usage are very unique, as there were no earlier comprehensive descriptions of similar surgical instruments by any surgeon, not only in India but also the whole world. Sushruta was perhaps the first surgeon in the world to describe different types of surgical instruments including endoscopes. This is far beyond the imagination of any other surgeon at that period [5].

SHALYATANTRA- SURGICAL TECHNIQUES

Sushruta was a great Indian surgeon and is the author of the book Sushruta Samhita describes over 120 surgical instruments 300 surgical procedures and classifies human surgery in 8 categories. He described the surgery as the first and foremost specialty of the system. He describes various surgical procedures including abdominal operations like those for intestinal obstruction and stones in the bladder. Because of his numerous contributions to the science and art of surgery he is known by the title “Father of Surgery.” Sushruta was the first surgeon to develop cosmetic surgery. He is also known as the “Father of plastic surgery” as he was the first person to describe and practice plastic surgery. He similarly performed rhinoplasty by plastic surgeons of today's era [6].

Fig.1: Sushruta are doping surgery[6]

Plastic Surgery by Sushruta

Sushruta an ancient plastic surgeon is the earliest surgeon of history during 600 B.C., and it is also believed to be the first and foremost popular person to invent and describe plastic surgery. The basic principles of plastic surgery were described by him in his famous ancient treatise "Sushruta Samhita". Most of the people consider Plastic Surgery as a comparatively new technique to improve physical beauty, the fact is its origin had roots over 4000 years old in India. Hindu mythology consists of four Vedas - namely the Rig Veda, Sama Veda, Yajur Veda, and Atharva Veda. It is believed that **Sushruta Samhita** to be a part of Atharva Veda. Sushruta an ancient plastic surgeon is not known, however, many scholars believe that between 600 and 1000 BC. Many researchers up to 9 in number are called Sushruta lived, taught as well as practicing his art in the city of Varanasi [7].

The followers of Sushruta were called as Sushruta. The new student was expected to study for at least 6 years. Before starting his training he had to take a solemn oath, which can be compared to that of Hippocrates. He taught the surgical skills to his students on various experimental modules, for instance, incision on vegetables (like watermelon, gourd, cucumber etc.), probing on worm-eaten wood, and preceding present-day workshops by more than 2600 years. 'Sushruta' were doing mock surgeries on gourds, watermelons, cucumbers.

Fig.2: Sushruta doing mock surgeries on gourds, watermelons, cucumbers [7]

Sushruta Samhita book contains 184 chapters, 1,120 conditions are listed, including injuries and illnesses relating to aging and mental illness. The compendium of Sushruta includes many chapters on the training and practice of surgeons.

All the basic principles of plastic surgery like planning, precision, hemostasis, and perfection find an important place in Sushruta's writings on this subject. Sushruta described various reconstructive methods or different types of defects like release of the skin for covering small defects, rotation of the flaps to make up for the partial loss, and pedicle flaps for covering complete loss of skin from an area [8].

Origin of Rhinoplasty

Rhinoplasty, colloquially known as the 'nose job,' is a surgery performed to achieve two results:

- To improve the breathing function of the nose
- To improve the cosmetic look of the nose

Sushruta's treatise provides the **first written record of a forehead flap rhinoplasty, a technique still used today to reconstruct a nose**. He used a flap of skin from the forehead, called a pedicle, to form a new nose.

The nose in Indian society has remained a symbol of dignity and respect throughout antiquity. In ancient times, amputation of the nose was frequently done as a punishment for criminals, war prisoners or people indulged in adultery [9].

The practice of Rhinoplasty slowly started as a result of the need to reconstruct the external nose and later developed to full-fledged science.

Fig.3: Rhinoplasty: Reconstruction of nose through plastic surgery [10]

Surgical instruments

These instruments are twenty in number such as the Mandalagra, the Karapatra, the Vriddhipatra, the Nakhasastram, the Mudrika, the Utpalapatra, the Arddhadhara, the Suchi, the Kushapatra, the atemukha, the Shararimukha, the Antarmukha, the Trikurchaka, the Kutharika, the Vrihimukha, the Ara, the Vetasapatra, the Vadisha, the Dantashanku, and the Eshani.

Fig.4: Surgical Instruments menion inshushurta samitha [9]

The kutharika (small, blunt axe) measures seven fingers and a half in the handle, the blade is half a finger in width and is blunted like the tooth of a cow. The Vrihimukha measures six fingers in its entire length and its top is like that of a Vrihi seed, and the edge is cut into small thornlike projections. The Ara resembles the awl of a cobbler and measures ten fingers in its entire length, the blade is wide as the seed of a sesamum and has the girth of a Durva (grass) stem. The Vetasapatra (knife) resembles the leaf of a Vetasa plant. The blade is four fingers in length, one finger in width, and is keenly edged, the handle measuring four fingers in length. The Vadisha is shaped like a modern fishing hook. The Danta-shanku (pincers for extracting teeth) somewhat resembles the Vrihimukha in shape. The face of an Eshani (probe) is like that of a Gandupada (earth-worm). of the above said instruments, the Mandalagra and the Karapatra should be used in incising and scraping. The Vriddhipatra, the Nakhasastra, the Mudrika, the Utpalapatra, and the Arddhadhara, should be employed in incising (Chedana) and excising (Bhedana); and the Kushapatra, the Shuchi, the atemukha, the Shararimukha, the Trikurchaka and the Antarmukha should be made use of in exudating or secreting (Visravana). The Kutharika, the Vrihimukha, the Ara, the Vetasapatra, and the Suchi (needle) should be used in puncturing. The Vadisha and the Danta-Shanku

should be used in extracting solid bodies. The Eshani (probe or director) in probing or searching the course or direction of the pus (in a suppurated part), and the Suchi (needle) should be used in suturing. Thus we have explained the eight different functions of the instruments in connection with surgical operations [11].

Now we shall deal with the mode of handling the abovesaid instruments. —The Vriddhipatra and other instruments for excising (Bhedana) should be caught hold of at a part between the blade and the handle. In acts of scraping the Vriddhipatra and the Mandalagra should be handled with the palm of the hand slightly turned up. The instruments for secreting should be caught hold of at the roots of their blades at the time of using them, while in the case of a king, an old man, a timid or a delicate person, a child, a woman and especially in the case of a prince of the royal blood, the Trikurchaka should be used when any secreting or exudating operation would be necessary. The handle of a Vrihimukha should be kept concealed within the palm of the hand and the blade should be caught hold of with the thumb and the index finger (Pradeshini). The Kutharika should be first supported on the left hand and then struck with the thumb and third finger of the right. The Ara, the Karapatra, and the Eshani, should be caught hold of at their roots. The rest of the surgical instruments should be grappled according to requirements.

The abovesaid instruments are shaped like things which their very names imply, as have been already described. The Nakashastram and the Eshani measure eight fingers in length. The Suchi (needle) shall be described later on. The top-ends of the Vadisha and the Danta-Shankhu Dental pincers are a little bent down and their faces are made to resemble sharp thorns or the newly sprouted leaves of a barley plant. The top-end of an Eshani closely resembles the mouth of an earth-worm. The length of a Mudrika should be made equal to that of the top phalanges of the index finger (of a man of average height.) A Shararimukha measures ten fingers in length. The rest of the instruments are mostly made to measure six fingers in length.

Admirable features in a Surgical instrument mention in shushurta samitha:—

Instruments that are fitted with handles of easy grip and are made of good and pure iron, well-shaped, sharp, and are set with edges that are not jagged and end in well-formed points or tops, should be deemed as the best of their kind.

Curvature, bluntness Kuntha—lit: -incapable of cutting hair, unequal sharpness of the edge, rough-edginess, over-thickness, over-thinness, over-lengthiness, and over-shortness are the defective traits in a surgical instrument. Those possessed of contrary features should be used. But a Karapatra set with a very rough (dentated) edge may be used to saw the bones.

A surgical instrument meant for excision bhedana should be set with an edge as thin as that of a Musurapulse lentil seed, while an instrument used in scraping should be set with an edge half as thin as that of the former. An instrument used either in connection with the measures of secretion or cutting by uplifting (Vyadhana) should be set with an edge as fine as the human hair, while an instrument of incision should have an edge half as thin as that of the former [12].

Surgical instruments should be tempered with one of the three substances such as alkali, water, and oil. Instruments used in cutting an arrow, a bone, or any foreign matter (Shalya) pricked into the human body, should be tempered with alkali, whereas those that are made use of in cutting, cleaving, and lopping off the flesh (from an affected part), should be tempered with water. Instruments used in opening Vyadhana a vein (Shira) or in cutting open a nerve Snayu should be tempered with oil, and should be whetted upon a species of stone-slab resembling a Masha pulse in colour, and their set-edge should be protected by putting it in a sheath made of Shalmali wood.

Substitutive instruments (the Anu-Shastras): —

The skin of bamboos, crystals, bits of glass, Kuruvindas (a sort of crystal) leeches, fire, alkali, nails, the leaves of trees known as Goji, Shephalika and Shakapatra, the tender sprouts of corn, hair, and the fingers, should be included within the category of the minor instruments of surgery and (which may be used in certain instances in substitution for the principal and usual ones.

Material study: —

The four articles such as strips of bamboo skin, crystals, bits of glass, and the rock is known as Kuruvinda, should be used by an intelligent physician in incising or excising (Bhedana) operations, where the patient would be found to have a dread of the knife, or too young to be surgically operated upon with it, or where the proper instrument cannot be procured. The nails of fingers should be used in operations of incising, excising or extracting in (substitution for the instruments enjoined to be used for the purpose), when such a course would appear feasible. The processes of applying alkalis, leeches, and cauterization will be dealt with later on. In Diseases affecting the eyelids or the cavity of the mouth, operations for the purposes of secreting or evacuating (the accumulated pus or phlegm), may be performed with the leaves of Shakapatra, Shephalika, or Gojis. In the absence of a probe or director, searching may be done with the help of a finger, or with a hair, or with a corn sprout. An intelligent physician should deem it is imperative duty to get his surgical instruments made by a skillful and experienced blacksmith and of pure, strong, and sharp iron (steel). A physician, skilled in the art of using surgical instruments, is always successful in his professional practice, and hence the practice of surgery should be commenced at the very outset of medical studies [12].

Conclusion

The Sushruta Samhita is a text whose authenticity is questioned a lot, but it is still cited as one of the first and most important pieces of surgical history. The area of plastic surgery has gained immensely from the Sushruta Samhita teachings and is exemplified by the Rhinoplasty method. The root of the practice from the Sushruta Samhita should not be ignored, although it is a historical text in which much of the techniques will not be performed in the current climate, and sometimes the underlying method of the surgery is the same, but more advanced instruments and medications are now available for the procedure. The Sushruta Samhita exemplifies this trend as it moved away from the pre-historic and primitive practices of surgery and allowed a codified set of rules for surgery to be presented which made the overall experience for the patient safer.

In order to maintain an acceptable quality of treatment, the use of specialized surgical instruments and proper preparation for surgeons is a prerequisite to the extensive training that doctors must receive during current training. With the increased potential use in surgical practice of Robot-Assisted surgery and Artificial Intelligence, surgery becomes very easy but the contribution of Sushruta Samhita is also great.

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